

Capitalist Transitions of Sustainability in the Post-Growth Economy

The absence of collective values of Sustainability in contemporary architecture as a result of capitalist emphasis on technological interventions and market-driven values

Faculty of Architecture, Urbanism and Building Technology

Delft Lectures on Architectural History and Theory

Course Code: AR1A066

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Submitted on 21 April 2023

Abstract

The inauguration of sustainability in the late 20th century marked a crucial turning point in the pursuit of harmonious coexistence between humanity and the finite nature of our planet. At the core of this concept lies the self-generating trinity of economy, resources, and society. However, this study contends that the fundamental transformation required to achieve collective sustainability necessitates the substitution of the capitalist system of production, which inherently hinders the potential of sustainable values.

Regrettably, the collective values of sustainability have failed to attain economic, social, and environmental equilibrium due to the overemphasis on the economic aspect of the concept within the current capitalist order. This emphasis favours technological intervention as a means of capital accumulation through the introduction of new market segments that promote environmental awareness. Notably, the influence of this overemphasized economic value of sustainability in architecture misleads the complex definition of sustainability toward technological solutions for creating sustainable buildings due to their high market value. Therefore, it is essential to understand whose version of sustainability we seek to promote: one that targets the reconciliation of humans with nature or the regeneration of financial opportunities through addressing continuous symptoms of climate change rather than the root causes. This study identifies the latter as the current state of sustainability, driven by the technological advancements that capture public attention. As Dr. Walter Stahel of ETH opines, “*We cannot solve the ecological and social challenges of the built environment by technological means alone.*” (Stahel, 2016) The challenge is to preserve the desired economic interaction while prioritizing circularity in our consumption and production, which will be necessary to deliver the true values of sustainability to the reconciliation of humans, capitalism, and nature, rather than perpetuating the finite system’s continuous exploitation.

Overall, this study proposes a novel perspective on how we perceive and define sustainability in the built environment as a distorted transition of the concept that unconsciously shapes our beliefs in favour of the capitalist order. Consequently, this argument seeks to demonstrate the interrelations between the features of the capitalist market and their problematic consequences for establishing genuine sustainability. Thus, this study speculates potential solutions by differentiating between the principles of market and technological interventions.

Keywords: Sustainability, Capitalism, Technology, Distortion, Market

1. The New Normal

The discourse of sustainability and architecture has been continuously marked by the tensions between the need for imperative environmental responsibility, holistic design solutions, and innovative technology. The statement of *Sally Uren*, the influential CEO of *Forum for the Future* becomes the departing point of the paper:

“Marketing sustainability is now a business strategy, as opposed to a corporate responsibility strategy. It is not only an opportunity to reduce costs, but also a means to tap into new market segments, differentiate products and services, and gain a competitive advantage” (greenbusinessbureau, 2022).

The contemporary perception of sustainability has shifted from a corporate responsibility issue to a strategic marketing opportunity, where businesses in a capitalist economy can implement the concept of sustainability as a catalyst for a strong market value. This becomes the driving force of the capitalist transition of sustainability. The stated *competitive advantage* can be translated into a greater profit through increased market share which implies that the pervasive trend to ‘heal’ the planet is beyond the boundary of environmental awareness, and reached the point where the embracement of sustainability in architectural businesses became an integral part of a value proposition.

Within this value-focused capitalist market, the architectural industry is continuously expanding within the finite system of the Earth, shifting our ways of positioning the concept of sustainability towards the optimal way to comply with economic development and capital accumulation. In the present post-growth economy, this economic development has been majorly carried out by the advancement of technology and greatly transformed the global trend of production and consumption to utilize technological interventions to achieve financial prosperity (Brynjolfsson&McAfee 2014). Thus, the impact of the profit-driven nature on collective values of sustainability leads to the natural focus on lucrative opportunities: technological interventions as a conspicuous marketing strategy in combination with the demand for positive environmental impact. This has resulted in a limited view of the concept of sustainability, which is narrowly defined by technological interventions aimed at generating profit, superficially neglecting the social and environmental choices that are truly necessary to achieve the original objective.

This paper problematizes how the contemporary view of sustainability as a business strategy and a new market segment resulted in the architectural industry’s over-reliance on technological interventions. The present capitalist market system has therefore caused a colossal shift in the definition from the historical meaning of sustainability, that was first reported in 1987 United Nations’ World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED, 1987). Overall, through the comparison between the historical and present modes of sustainability, the paper generates a novel perspective that the fundamental contradictions between the profit-centered market system and the concept of sustainability have occurred in the post-growth economy, as capitalism is predisposed to an overemphasis on technological intervention as a way of achieving sustainability because it is seen as a source of profitable innovation.

The reciprocal relationship between three actors: sustainability, capitalism, and technology is elucidated to be inseparable in the contemporary trend of environmental awareness and capital accumulation. The technological intervention itself is certainly a strong asset for humanity to withstand the symptoms of climate change, regardless of the business objective. Thus, the direction of the paper is not aiming to strongly disapprove the ineffectiveness of the current model of sustainability in capitalism nor to criticize the insufficient technological solutions in sustainable built-environment but rather aims to critically re-think how the complex nature of sustainability has been simplified to technological advancement per se, in order to be adjusted to the contemporary development of the capitalist ecology. Eventually, in addition to the existing technological intervention addressing the “symptoms”, a novel alternative to amalgamate the collective values of sustainability with a profit-based economy can be speculated.

2. The Transition: Evolution or Distortion?

Almost everything in the finite system evolves through the dynamic interaction between organisms and chronological development. Humans evolved, and so did language, culture, bipedalism, and the brain. Mention a further example, the evolution of the peppered moth, where the pollution caused the trees to become darker, making the light-coloured moths change darker to be camouflaged. This resembles the current situation of humanity, finding a route to evolve systemically, within the polluted environment of the finite planet. However, is this an evolution? Whether it is a biological or systemic alteration, it has already been broadly proven that living things and conditions evolve in the finite world due to natural selection, as Darwin's Theory of Evolution describes: *which is the process by which organisms that are better adapted to their environment are more likely to survive and reproduce* (Infinitylearn,2023). Distortion and evolution are both concepts that involve change over time, which forms the transition. To be specific, distortion shares a common feature as the concept of evolution due to the common alteration in the appearance, shape, sound, and interpretation of a certain target. The boundary between evolution and distortion is shallow enough to be simply regarded as a cause-and-effect, where the evolution is caused by the distortion or vice-versa. However, we should not under-estimate this shallow boundary between these two concepts as the main difference is the "intention". The paper first begins with questioning the intentions of sustainability to examine whether it has been distorted to be interpreted to suit the ecology of capitalism and contemporary built-environment or naturally evolved as a result of the purpose of adapting to rapidly changing climate and living conditions, for the survival of human-being, in response to changing environments just like the moths.

Let's first expand the chronological sequence of the term *market* in order to identify the intention of sustainability under the ecology of capitalism. The introduction of money as a medium of exchange helped to overcome the limitations of bartering, which emerged as early as 3000 BC, as it allowed for more efficient and convenient trade. Markets, therefore, emerged as a way for buyers and sellers to come together and exchange goods and services at agreed-upon prices. Markets facilitated the growth of trade and commerce, as well as the development of complex societies and economies (Niall Ferguson,2008). Today, money and markets are integral parts of modern global economic systems that operate the capitalist economy. Undoubtedly, this is an evolution of trading methods to intentionally solve the limitations of the previous generation. How about the term sustainability?

"It is a notion that is everywhere, but no one seems to know exactly what it means." This is adapted from Joshua Bolchover who provides a critical perspective on sustainable design through *"Vitamin Green"*, to elucidate the starting point of the transitions of the term sustainability. His statement of *"no one knows"* already foreshadows that the definition of sustainability has been distorted. The missing intention of the change is clear evidence. Followed by the introduction of the term sustainability by the United Nations in 1987, the US Environmental Protection Agency defines the term as:

"to create and maintain conditions under which humans and nature can exist in productive harmony, that permit fulfilling the social, economic, and other requirements of present and future generations" (EPA,2023).

Thus, the original concept was holistically human-centered, and the term was predominantly used among ecologists and environmental economists for the preservation of civilized humanity rather than the protection of the capitalist framework per se. However, the pervasive use of the term "sustainability" in the field of contemporary architecture as part of the new marketing strategy, has resulted in distorting the original meaning to the point where it has become almost synonymous with "good," while adding multiple definitions when the term was adapted to architecture from the economic development, specifically adjusting to the capitalist context. The "sustainability" and "green" labels are increasingly found on the websites of architecture firms. Eventually, the misuse and abuse of the concept of "sustainability" have led to its vagueness, allowing the term to be freely used in architecture, and the diversity of definitions has resulted in various ways to achieve them (Lance.H, 2020). This is seen through the post-growth economy's inability to tolerate the meaning of truthful sustainability, using the word as a vague reference to resource conservation alone through technological advancements and for the increased value of their projects.

Our current understanding of sustainability has evolved intending to adapt to and survive within the framework of capitalism, simultaneously progressing naturally with economic growth over time. The paper also identifies the inauguration of the concept of sustainability by the WCED in 1987 as an introduction to the evolution of human behavior, intentionally adjusting the economic condition to a rapidly changing climate. Unfortunately, it is the definition of sustainability that has been distorted, resulting from its unintentional alteration by the market system, which has superficially repositioned the meaning of sustainability to create a new market segment for profit, thereby becoming influenced by capitalist principles and contributing towards the capitalist transitions of sustainability.

3. Core Market Systems: The Barriers

The core of capitalism is operated based on the form of “Markets”. Mankiw’s seminal principles of economics define the markets as “*groups of buyers and sellers of a particular good or service*” (Mankiw, 2014). From the interpretation, the buyers determine the demand, and the sellers determine the supply, which is a common form of architectural business. From a contradicting perspective, one could regard this broad statement as an oversimplification of the vast plurality of market-mediated social relations through a theoretical lens. However, the paper is not aiming to elucidate a complex market system through a detailed analysis - which has been already carried out by others such as Marx - but rather aims to identify fundamental features that define market systems. Through this identification, it becomes possible to problematize how these features affect the potential of sustainability in the capitalist built environment -leading to the capitalist transitions of sustainability while proposing alternative perspectives on root causes of the critical failure of harmonizing two actors: sustainability and capitalism. Following the form of a supply and demand chain, it is vital to understand how the industry operates within the post-growth economy in relation to the original objectives of sustainability. The paper suggests that the fundamental market system in architecture is divided into 4 sectors, which in combination become a backstage for the contemporary transition of sustainability: private property, competition, human labour, and price, which is determined by the level and urgency of demand and consumption.

The first core system, the protection of private property is potentially the most visible pillar to exist in the post-growth economy because the capitalist framework identifies this as a general foundational axiom of human rights. In the context of architecture, private property protection can lead to a significant challenge in achieving sustainability. It limits the ability of communities and governments to regulate the use of land and buildings for the public good. In this sense, private property protection can be seen as an obstacle to the long-term objective of sustainability in the built environment. Ultimately, the protection of private property led to the new transition of the sustainability concept, to be adjusted following the logic of passive revolution. This eventually led to the transformation of the sustainability structures without strong social processes for their self-preservation.

The second core system, competition defines market dynamics in the architectural industry and forms an equilibrium in the prices of services, materials, and labour. The aggregated behavior of the architectural industry intensifies competition between businesses in the capitalist economy, becoming a catalyst of technological interventions. This intervention is highly emphasized by corporations for self-preservation and distinctive market features to gain an advantage.

Human labour in capitalism plays a vital role as a third core system. The previously mentioned two cores are understandably linked with the transitions of the objective of sustainability, but it may be challenging to identify the conspicuous impact of labour towards the current model of sustainability in the post-growth economic system. However, the way the capitalist framework treats the market leaves a clear hint. Human labour is visible as a tradable good, where the combination of time and skills are exchanged for wages. Therefore, it is inextricably associated with human lives - specifically financial stability. For instance, if a business faces a severe financial crisis, the lives of employees are at stake, highlighting the extreme fragility of human life. Thus, labour is highly dependent on workers’ own financial sustainability before prioritising the value of nature and holistic development. This reflects the Darwinian evolutionary theory of “survival of the fittest”, which in capitalism, superficially transforms the concept of sustainability to a simple cause-and-effect relationship between survival and finance.

Lastly, price is another core system, which is majorly determined by the level of supply and demand. Within a capitalist system, value is only limited to products that possess market prices. This is one of the major reasons for sustainability's emphasis on technology because it has a strong market value. As a result, the post-growth economy's inability to assign value to a system that has no market prices is a critical issue, which raises a critical concern towards the current implication of sustainability, transitioning into a market efficiency against its original objectives. In the next subsections, the paper will examine these four core systems and problematize that the current model of sustainability is transformed by the capitalist framework, which results in narrowing the complex collective values of sustainability to a technological intervention alone in contemporary architecture.

4. Market Drives the Superficial Trend

Calls for addressing climate change, global warming, carbon emissions, and environmental catastrophes can be increasingly heard in the public sphere nowadays (BBC, 2019). Potentially, it is almost hypocritical as these calls are seemingly contradictory to what humans have been developing so far: the economic system that naturally exploits nature. Media outlets and corporations are all advocating for action, boasting to be the positive protagonist against this crisis. These so-called influencers largely affect the market force, shaping a direction in which industries are developing into sustainable projects, showcasing their innovative technological solutions and designs, and attracting public attention. This is where a "trend" begins.

As addressed by the second core system of competition, capitalism is sensitive to where people focus, because it operates on the basic principle of supply and demand. Specifically in architecture, designs typically emerge from where a problem arises, in which the problem becomes the demand. Businesses naturally seek to maximise profits by directly responding to services that are in high demand, because this is how they remain competitive and profitable. *Figure 1* demonstrates the close relationship between the different technological eras and economic activity, and it is observable that the new technological intervention elevates economic activity, leading to infinite financial influx through the continuous generation of new phases of technological limits. Thus, the trend is undeniably dependent on technology, because it is the biggest driving force of economic expansion, but also an indicator of a new capacity. Steam and steel railway introduced the radical transformation of material transportation trends in architecture, digital networks, and software opening a new trend of social media and online communication for collaborative design, virtual reality, and online training. Demonstrated by the alteration of trends, technology is the creator of new opportunities, where sustainability is the next phase of not just architecture but the entire human evolution. However, this raises a critical concern because the capitalist economy operates through the motivation of profit. It is crucial to consider technology as a collaborator rather than a panacea due to the inherent character of capitalist technology, which tends to focus on addressing symptoms rather than root causes, in pursuit of perpetual growth. The reluctance of capitalist technology to address underlying causes stems from the absence of causative factors, which translates into a lack of profit motive.

Figure 1: Economic Activity Based on Technological Interventions - Schumpeter's long Waves of Innovation (Sokolov, M. 2019)

Innovative technology has been implemented for decades to tackle the global issue of exacerbating climate change, ranging from electric transport and eco-friendly materials to renewable energy and energy storage. However, the notion of sustainability embedded within the capitalist architecture is a complex matter that cannot be addressed solely through technical methods. Therefore, the underlying social, economic, and political systems are deeply intertwined with the framework of capitalism. For instance, although renewable energy sources can greatly contribute to decreased greenhouse gas emissions and mitigate continuous symptoms of climate change, the fundamental causes of this problem necessitate significant alterations in the economic and social systems that rely on fossil fuels and perpetuate the linear economy of unsustainable consumption and production. Relatedly, waste management can be improved by reducing waste through recycling and other means. However, to truly alleviate the underlying causes of this issue, the economic and social systems that prioritize disposability and single-use products must be transformed. Therefore, the integration of sustainability and capitalism necessitates a complete economic system overhaul, with a shift from independent technical advancements towards a circular economy. The approach should prioritize collective values of sustainability, economic development, and the global trend towards climate urgency.

5. Infinite Growth is a Paradox

The mutual development of capitalism and technology implies that the relationship between the growth of the economy and technology is directly proportional. The previously-mentioned four market core systems reveal the problematic outcome of the architectural industry within the capitalist ecology: the system of continuous production through exploitation and infinite growth. The current intervention in sustainability certainly expands the market opportunity and is widely implemented as a response to the global trend of climate awareness. However, infinite growth is incompatible with the finite planet Earth and antithetical to the nature of sustainability because natural systems do not grow infinitely, but reaches the equilibrium with the ecosystem (Siderius&Zink, 2022). The current economic system is built upon the concept of planned obsolescence, which encourages consumers to continually replace their products for the infinite growth of the market through the loop of consumption and production, resulting in a massive waste stream that exacerbates the environmental crisis in a linear economy. This is where the technology is even more favoured in this market system because it continuously gets updated as the trend evolves, naturally attracting the public attention to replace the latest innovative technology, which is a paradoxical behavior of so-called sustainable product users and suppliers (Figure 2), replacing a sustainable device for the “better sustainability”. Consequently, the truthful values of sustainability cannot be achieved within the capitalist system that requires infinite growth and the preservation of financial accumulation, without the colossal transition of the meaning of sustainability itself to comply with economic growth. Highlighting behind the scene of capitalist transitions of sustainability.

Figure 2 :Increasing PV Panel Wastes as PV Capacity Increases in the future (PV Magazine, 2022)

It is therefore critical to understand from the perspective of capitalism: why the original objective of sustainability has to be shifted rather than the economy itself. Firstly, growth is addictive. Due to the perception that human consumption desires are infinite and insatiable (Fisher, 2017). Secondly, the second market core system of competition promotes the desire to grow and compete against the “rivals”. Lastly, the concept of sustainability will naturally obey the logic of profit and capital accumulation as Marx stated as “*passive revolution(1)*” in the context of the capitalist framework (Wanner, 2014).

(1) *Passive revolution* refers to a process in which the ruling class is able to maintain their power and control by adapting to the changing social and economic conditions through minor reforms that preserve the existing power structure (Heller, A., & Feher, F. (1987). *Gramsci and Foucault: A Reassessment*. Humanities Press Intl)

6. The Influence on Building Codes

Following the supply and demand system in capitalism, a new challenge for the architectural industry was to embrace sustainability as an integral part of their value proposition. To combat the ambiguity of sustainability and quantifiably authenticate a building's green impact, eco-friendliness, and well-being, rating systems such as BREEAM, DGNB, and UK Approved Document L1: Conservation of Fuel and Power have been developed. However, these systems often put less emphasis on soft issues such as cultural and social values, including equity, and oversimplify the complexity of sustainability into a technological tick-box, only requiring it to satisfy the environmental criteria that those systems demand - the quantifiable standards. There is a distinctive common feature among these sustainable building codes: the predominant emphasis on technological solutions based on the scientific and statistical data of energy consumption, which are emphasizing addressing the symptoms of climate change. The paper does not intend to criticise the technological interventions but rather suggests that technology itself should not be treated as the only definition to reach the objectives of sustainability like the existing codes demonstrate. Thus, in addition to technological interventions, sustainable building codes should address the economy of consumption and production, to deal with the causes - not only the symptoms- of climate change.

The problematic consequence of the capitalist market system is certainly affecting the way we assess and envision sustainability because the market favours technically suboptimal systems. As mentioned above, this is due to the principle of competition for cost benefits that prioritizes net present value. The most popular sustainability certification system for the architecture and real estate industry is BREEAM or Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method. In the current market, BREEAM-qualified buildings are strongly defined as 'Sustainable'. The assessment method includes six certification levels: unclassified to outstanding, to quantifiably assess the contribution to the environment. The intention of this system is not only to assess the environmental contribution but also simultaneously add value to each of the project's stakeholders. This characteristic has been already pointed out by the second and fourth market core systems of "Competition" and "price", which is proven by such an assessment system that the highest weighting in the BREEAM ranking is completely energy-related (Eric.R, 2022) - 9 factors called ENE01 - ENE09. This assessment system specifically focuses on the active analysis of energy use and emissions (figure3), requiring the implementation of low-consumption devices to achieve their definition of sustainability. Thus, the majority of energy use in a commercial building is accounted for by HVAC, refrigeration, and lighting systems. As a result, the developers' attention to these issues becomes the top priority, regardless of their environmental awareness, simply because it adds to the Market Prices. Smart technologies combined with a sophisticated design concept is, therefore, the key solution to the highest BREEAM level within the linear economy of capitalism, completely neglecting the complex circular economy of consumption and production. In addition to missing consideration of the circularity of a building, BREEAM's lack of consideration for disabilities and affordability for low-income populations is the key evidence that it targets the financial accumulation behind the facade of sustainability.

Figure 3: BREEAM Credit Categories & Credit Points: High Priority on Technological Solutions

As an example, the over-emphasis of sustainable projects on technology can be explained with one of the most ambitious sustainable projects by a leading architectural practice: The Masdar City by fosters and partners. The plan included a tremendous amount of PV panels and the area was carefully designed for pedestrians where roads are technically designed to catch the wind that moves between the desert and the Gulf, providing a streetscape that does not require vehicles and air-conditioning system. This innovative design is based on the plans of old Arabic cities, which questions the necessity of expensive high-tech systems to imitate traditional sustainable urbanism.

Despite the aim of carbon-neutrality, the construction required tremendous amount of energy, imported materials and sustaining the city will be unsustainable due to the location that is limited to freshwater (McArdle, M. 2018). The Masdar City satisfied most of the quantifiable building codes such as “self-sufficiency” of energy through the required amount of PV Panels, green roofs and water-harvesting system but not necessarily satisfying the original definition of sustainability - “holistic development for the future generation”. It is clear that the certification is not truly addressing the collective values of sustainability. Thus, the paper speculates a mediation solution by including the assesment on the level of circularity in addition to technological criteria within the building codes. This may significantly raise the difficulties of achieving BREEAM in the architecture industry, but this implies how we have been broadly generous with over-simplifying the collective values of sustainability as a result of favouring capitalist backstage. Furthermore, this paper anticipates that this increased difficulty will in fact, add even higher market value to the new BREEAM-certified buildings, as they will possess more distinctive high-standard features to stand-out in the competitive market, demonstrated by the second core market system of competition. Therefore, this novel mediation solution of applying circular economy concept to quantifiable assessments will not only increase the market prices but address both symptoms and causes of the anti-sustainable behaviour of existing capitalist economy.

7. The Dangerous Comfort

The prevailing market assumption that technology will always be the panacea for social and environmental challenges is a critical concern in contemporary sustainability discourse. This belief system is prone to trigger a fundamental breakdown in the implementation of collective values of sustainability. The paper has been elucidating that the notion of sustainability in capitalism certainly overlooks the social and cultural aspects of sustainability, hence failing to acknowledge that holistic alterations to achieve truthful sustainability require shifts in values, beliefs, and lifestyles, rather than the mere adoption of innovative technological advancements in the finite system of our planet. Secondly, this premise dangerously nurtures a false sense of security, which would eventually lead to complacency about the scope and urgency of the environmental and social challenges confronting humanity. Finally, it strongly reinforces the very problems that it aims to resolve by emphasizing the perception that economic growth, financial prosperity and technological innovation are the sole solutions to social and environmental problems, while sidelining alternative approaches centered on sufficiency, equity, and resilience (Tim Jackson, 2017).

Therefore, the capitalist transformation of the notion of sustainability is not just a matter of simplifying complex values. This process of simplification may not be the most optimal approach in the finite system as it overlooks the collective values of sustainability that are crucial for realising a sustainable future.

8. Re-thinking Priorities

The contemporary economic system, which is rooted in capitalist ideology, has been structured to prioritize market efficiency, competition, infinite growth, and profit maximization. As a consequence, collective values of sustainability have been subjugated to meet the needs of the market, rather than addressing the genuine needs of humans such as human well-being. Although technological advancements have been proposed as the most influential solutions to sustainability challenges currently, their effectiveness is directly limited by the capitalist economy of the current economic system, prioritizing market success. Therefore, it is speculated that a paradigm shift in priorities is necessary, moving away from the emphasis on market efficiency and towards prioritizing human needs rather than market needs, and endorsing non-market and democratic methods of achieving sustainability.

The example of the NASA Apollo program demonstrates how collective values and objectives can be achieved, even in the absence of clear market demand. Harrison Schmitt, the astronaut even stated that governments are too inefficient for a return to the moon, which he was referring to market inefficiency (Ghosh, P, 2012). The Apollo program was not motivated by profit, because there was no existing supply or demand curve, but rather operated by the collective goal of sending a human to the moon. It exemplifies the potential for collective values to drive innovation and progress, independent of market forces. In the context of sustainability and capitalism, this example underscores the need to prioritize collective values over market forces and to challenge the current economic paradigm to achieve a more holistic approach to sustainability that acknowledges and incorporates fundamental human values.

9. Conclusions: An Attempt to Sustain the Unsustainable

From this fundamental premise, it is apparent that the existing capitalist system has evolved over the centuries with a specific intent of promoting behaviors that yield optimal outcomes for the market. As initially described by the four core systems of the capitalist market, the market-based system thrives on incentivizing competition rather than cooperation, prioritizes cost reduction and profit maximization, mandates growth, favours disaggregation over systemic design, and conflates price with value. The paper admits that the inauguration of the concept of sustainability is indeed a colossal step towards the preservation of human civilisation and certainly actively assists the economic expansion to be more responsible for the future generation and nature. However, the collective values of sustainability have been missed or at least greatly simplified to the stage that favours the preservation of capital accumulation, unconsciously shifting our beliefs that technology is the key answer to a sustainable built environment. Therefore, the current capitalist system of production is inherently at odds with the values of sustainability. The distortion of the definition of sustainability eventually led to the stage that favours technological intervention as a means of continuous capital accumulation. Consequently, this hypocritically exacerbated the gradual exploitation of linear economy of consumption and production in the pursuit of financial opportunities for the stronger relationship between humans and market prices, rather than the true reconciliation of humans and nature. Consequently, the paper concludes that the existing pillars of capitalism are inevitably designed to perform to the utmost through exploitation, which makes it completely unsustainable in the limited system of our planet. The sustainable technological intervention itself is only an attempt to sustain the unsustainable through addressing the continuously generating symptoms of climate change and it is vital to realize that this phenomenon only favours continuous economic growth rather than the collective aims of sustainability for the actual preservation of human-being.

Therefore, the study proposed a novel perspective on how we perceive and define sustainability in the built environment. It suggests that differentiating between the principles of market and technological interventions is necessary for establishing genuine sustainability in addition to moving away from the market forces. The challenge is to prioritize circularity in consumption and production while preserving the desired economic interaction, which will require a fundamental transformation of the current capitalist system. In conclusion, this study highlights the problematic interrelations between the features of the capitalist market and genuine sustainability values. It underscores the urgent need for a fundamental transformation of the current system and proposes potential solutions that prioritize circularity in consumption and production.

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